

Skin Cancer Prevention Through the Promotion of Sun Protection Behaviors at Work:

A Systematic Review of Randomized Control Trials

Rationale

Who use sunscreen regularly?

Alarming increase in the incidence rates of skin cancer (Sung et al., 2020).

The main extrinsic risk factor for skin cancer is exposure to solar ultraviolet radiation (UVR)

Andalusia (Southern Spain) is the region with more average hours (>2800) and clear days (>120) of Spain

Introduction

Some jobs/professions are particularly at risk

Key preventive measures (Green et al., 2011):

- ❑ Raising awareness and challenging certain ideas about sunbaths and tanning
- ❑ Regular sunscreen use

Research Question

(a) what are the most effective techniques to raise awareness about the risk of excessive exposure to UVR and promote sun protection behaviors at work?

(b) what explanatory models of behavior serve as the basis for skin cancer prevention programs in the workplace?

Method

Systematic review (PICOS and PRISMA)

P = Skin cancer

I = Prevention at work (promotion of protective behaviors)

C = Control or comparison group (RCT)

O = Quantitative intervention effectiveness

S = Working adults

Search = ("skin cancer") AND ("prevention") AND ("work*") AND ("control")

Articles in English, Spanish or Portuguese published between 2016-2022 and included in PubMed or Web of Science (WoS)

Results (I)

- Only 6 programs (11 articles)
 - USA x2
 - UK
 - Denmark
 - The Netherlands
 - Iran

Results (II)

- Overall, when the intervention group is compared with the control group, findings revealed that skin prevention programs are effective.
- Main theoretical frameworks
 - Diffusion of Innovations Theory (n = 6; Sun Safe Workplace program)
 - Protection Motivation Theory; Theory of Reasoned Action; Health Belief Model (HBM), Health Action Process Approach (HAPA), and Transtheoretical model of behaviour change.

Results (III)

- Methodological limitations and strenghts:
 - Few RCTs studies
 - Poor indicators to measure (implementation) effectiveness -> Only one (pilot) study included biomarkers (Keurentjes et al., 2021)
 - Lack of indicators of efficiency
- Sun Safe Workplaces: Evaluation at different analysis levels and follow-ups (Buller et al., 2018, 2019, 2021; Walcoz et al., 2018, 2020)

Conclusions (II)

- Context matters: Raising awareness is efficient (Houdmont et al., 2016) but may not be enough; and print-media campaigns may failure (Zink et al., 2018)
- Multicomponent interventions:
 - (1) persuading senior managers to adopt **solar safety policies** (see Sun Safe Workplace program);
 - (2) raising workers' **awareness** about the risk of skin cancer and how to reduce it;
 - (3) **providing sun protection equipment** (caps or shirts and long-sleeved vests) and sunscreens*; and
 - (4) facilitating **personalized messages** that remind workers the effective ways to protect themselves from the UVR (see also SunSmart program: Text messages via mobile phone).

*shadows and water

Thank You!

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